

TinySEED: A Lightweight Transformer Architecture with Channel-Attention for DDoS Detection

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Abstract

Uncovering stealthy Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks at the network-edge remains challenging due to increased system complexity and users' access to digital services. Therefore, in this work, we develop TinySEED, a lightweight yet accurate DDoS detection model based on TinyBERT that integrates a channel attention mechanism. TinyBERT is developed via knowledge distillation from BERT, providing a compact backbone that preserves key representational capacity while significantly reducing model size and inference latency. To further enhance discriminative power between DDoS attacks and benign traces, we integrate channel attention, which adaptively re-weights embedding channels (dimensions), enabling the model to capture fine-grained distinctions between benign and malicious flows that are often overlooked by distilled transformers. Extensive DDoS detection experiments across five benchmark datasets demonstrate that TinySEED consistently outperforms conventional machine learning methods, neural architectures, and transformer-based baselines. TinySEED achieves higher detection accuracy on benchmarks while maintaining low inference latency. These findings highlight the effectiveness of combining efficient transformer distillation with channel attention to achieve a practical and robust solution for low-latency DDoS detection in network-edge environments.

CCS Concepts

• Security and privacy → Denial-of-service attacks; • Computing methodologies → Neural networks; • Computer systems organization → Cloud computing.

Keywords

Cloud-edge network security, DDoS detection, Lightweight transformers, Channel attention

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1 Introduction

Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks have been a serious threat to networked systems since the late 1990s [28]. These attacks leverage networks of compromised devices (botnets) to generate both massive and stealthy malicious traffic that overwhelms target system resources and disrupts services. Despite extensive community efforts to develop effective defences, low-latency DDoS detection remains an open problem, as attackers have become increasingly sophisticated and continually leverage more infrastructure and services to generate volumetric and stealthy malicious traffic [40]. The largest recorded DDoS attack peaked at 11.5 terabits per second (Tbps)¹, and modern campaigns frequently employ simultaneous multi-vector attack strategies to bypass traditional defences. This escalation coincides with a shift in deployment toward the network edge, which extends the attack surface beyond centralized datacenters and into heterogeneous and resource-constrained edge environments.

As shown in Figure 1, the cloud-edge network architecture distributes computing capability across the continuum that includes intermediate edge nodes. This heterogeneity broadens exposures and weakens the defensive perimeter [30], as edge devices often operate with limited CPU, memory, and network capacity; control and telemetry are fragmented across domains, and mitigation must coordinate across diverse stacks and administrative boundaries. Therefore, stealthy and multi-vector DDoS traffic can degrade the Quality of Service (QoS) in such distributed environments, particularly for latency-sensitive applications (e.g., telemedicine or low-latency communications) where even minimal disruptions are unacceptable.

DDoS detection approaches rely on classical machine learning algorithms such as support vector machines, random forests [24, 31],

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¹"Cloudflare Blocks Record-Breaking 11.5 Tbps DDoS Attack," *The Hacker News*, September 3, 2025.

Figure 1: Conceptual cloud-edge network. The red dashed lines on the left denote DDoS attacks from the attacker group.

decision trees [27], and k-nearest neighbours [31] trained on hand-crafted flow or packet-level features. While these models can be effective on specific datasets, their performance depends heavily on manual feature engineering. They often struggle to capture complex spatio-temporal dependencies in modern network traces. More recent work has applied deep-learning architectures such as CNNs [14], LSTMs, and transformer-based models [10, 19] specifically to DDoS detection. In the context of DDoS, deep learning alleviates the need for manually crafted high-dimensional features by learning hierarchical temporal and spatial representations directly from network traces. However, these models typically require large labelled datasets and frequent retraining, which introduces significant computational overhead to meet the expected training performance. Transformer-based methods [10, 19], such as BERT [5, 21] have improved performance, but large parameter size and attention complexity lead to high per-sample inference cost and memory footprint, making them impractical for deployment in resource-constrained cloud-edge environments that require low latency and short inference times for DDoS detection [5, 21].

In this paper, we address the problem of uncovering DDoS attacks in cloud-edge networks while maintaining high detection accuracy, in particular for stealthy and multi-vector DDoS attacks with low detection latency requirements. To this end, we develop **TinySEED** (TinyBERT with channel attention for efficient DDoS detection), a novel model that combines TinyBERT, a compact version of BERT [13], with a lightweight channel attention mechanism to achieve both high detection accuracy and low inference time in network-edge environments. TinyBERT serves as a distilled transformer backbone, approximately 7–8× smaller and faster

than original BERT at inference time, while retaining essential representational capacity. The channel attention module adaptively re-weights channels along the embedding dimension, emphasizing the most informative traffic patterns and suppressing irrelevant signals with negligible inference time overhead. This integration preserves TinyBERT’s efficiency while significantly enhancing its ability to discriminate between benign and malicious flows, making TinySEED well-suited for low-latency DDoS detection across heterogeneous and resource-constrained network-edge environments. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose TinySEED², a DDoS detection model built on the TinyBERT transformer with a lightweight channel-attention module that adaptively re-weights embedding channels to highlight informative traffic dimensions. This enables fine-grained detection of stealthy DDoS attacks while preserving a compact design across heterogeneous edge environments.
- We conducted an exhaustive evaluation on five public DDoS benchmarks and found that TinySEED consistently outperforms conventional baselines, recent neural architectures, and transformer-based language models under diverse network conditions, demonstrating robust accuracy and strong generalization.
- We verified TinySEED achieves lower average per-sample inference latency than prior transformer-based methods, enabling its practical deployment across cloud-edge networks in resource-constrained environments.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work on DDoS detection. Section III details the

²<https://github.com/TinySEED-lab/TinySEED-TinyBERT>

proposed TinySEED detection framework, explaining the model architecture and the integration of the attention mechanism. Section IV describes the experimental setup and presents results from our evaluation, along with a discussion of the findings. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

2 Related Work

Research on DDoS detection has evolved considerably over the past two decades, moving from early rule-based and statistical methods to data-driven machine learning (ML) and, more recently, deep learning and transformer-based approaches. Each stage of this progression reflects a trade-off between detection accuracy, adaptability to new attack vectors, and computational efficiency. Baseline DDoS detection approaches are broadly categorized into conventional methods and language-model-based techniques, which are discussed in detail in the subsequent sections.

2.1 Conventional Detection Approaches

Classical ML methods, including decision trees, support vector machines, and random forests, have been extensively applied to DDoS detection. When trained on hand-crafted flow features, such models can achieve near-perfect performance on static benchmarks [4]. However, their effectiveness is limited against the dynamic and evolving characteristics of real-world DDoS traffic. Specifically, they lack the capacity to capture complex temporal dependencies and contextual patterns, making them vulnerable to evasion through novel attack strategies. Furthermore, the dependence on expert-engineered features hinders adaptability, resulting in poor generalization and limited robustness in high-throughput, low-latency detection scenarios [39]. Recent edge-side detectors based on information-theoretic correlation analysis illustrate these trade-offs: they reduce latency but still depend on hand-crafted statistics and thresholding, limiting adaptability to evolving attacks [2, 16].

Deep learning (DL) has substantially advanced DDoS detection by automatically extracting high-level traffic representations from raw flow data, thereby reducing reliance on manual feature engineering. For text-based protocols such as HTTP, NLP-style embeddings have also been applied to anomaly and malicious URL detection (e.g., Sec2vec) [15]. Empirical studies confirm that DL architectures—including Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and recurrent models such as Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit Networks (GRUs), consistently outperform classical ML baselines in detection accuracy [22]. CNNs are particularly effective at modelling spatial correlations in traffic features, whereas recurrent models capture the temporal dependency characteristic of evolving attack behaviours. Hybrid architectures, such as CNN-LSTM models, further improve robustness against complex and multi-class detection performance in Software-Defined Networking (SDN) environments. Despite these advances, DL-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) typically incur higher computational overhead, increased inference latency, and scalability limitations under high-throughput network conditions, highlighting the need for lightweight yet accurate detection models.

2.2 Language-based Detection Approaches

More recently, researchers have investigated transformer-based models for DDoS detection, inspired by their success in natural language processing. Transformer architectures, such as BERT, capture long-range dependencies and contextual patterns in sequential data, motivating the analogy of treating network traffic as a “language”. For instance, Dey et al. [6] propose a transformer model tailored for IoT network traffic, which processes features via self-attention and shows superior precision, recall, and F1-score over classical ML baselines on a real-world IoT dataset. Wang et al. [36] introduce DDoS-MSCT, a hybrid architecture combining multiscale convolutional modules with a transformer block. Specifically, a local feature extraction module using multiscale/dilated convolutions, and a global feature extraction module implementing multi-head self-attention, for joint capture of spatial and contextual traffic features. BERT-based IDSs have also proven effective: Heo et al. [10] introduce DDoSBERT (a fine-tuned BERT variant, distilbert-base-uncased-finetuned-sst-2-english), achieving state-of-the-art accuracy across multiple datasets; however, its performance degrades on cloud-integrated and large-scale datasets, indicating generalization limitations.

To sum up, despite substantial progress in DDoS detection, modern cloud-edge deployments raise an urgent need for efficient, lightweight, and adaptive defenses capable of handling rapidly evolving, multi-vector DDoS attacks. Our literature review found no prior approach that simultaneously meets the efficiency, low footprint, and adaptability required for practical cloud-edge systems. Existing methods typically trade off one or more of these requirements and therefore fall short in meeting the demands of day-to-day operation in such environments. To address this gap, we propose TinySEED, a compact transformer-based detector augmented with channel attention, which aims to provide competitive detection accuracy while satisfying the latency, resource, and adaptability constraints of cloud-edge systems.

3 Methodology

In this section, we describe the proposed TinySEED architecture for DDoS detection. The architecture includes a TinyBERT-6L model, a distilled BERT variant that substantially reduces the number of parameters and inference time compared to BERT-base (110M parameters) while preserving strong representational capacity [13], for learning feature representations of network traces, and a channel-attention mechanism for feature refinement. The subsequent sections provide detailed descriptions of these modules, and the overall framework of TinySEED is illustrated in Figure 2.

3.1 Backbone Module

To fully exploit the capabilities of language models, which are designed to process sequential text inputs, we first transform the network traffic features into textual sequences. In the process of converting a cleaned traffic flow with d features $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d]$ into a sequential textual expression, we linearize the feature vector into a textual expression separated by a special [SEP] symbol:

$$\mathbf{s} = [\text{CLS}] x_1 [\text{SEP}] x_2 [\text{SEP}] \cdots x_d [\text{SEP}], \quad (1)$$

Here, [CLS] is the classification token (start-of-sequence token here), and [SEP] is a feature delimiter. This conversion preserves feature-level information while allowing the language model to process the traffic as a sentence [3].

Once the sequential input \mathbf{s} is prepared, the tokenizer maps each token to an index $t_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ from the vocabulary \mathcal{V} :

$$\mathbf{t} = [t_0, t_1, \dots, t_n], \quad t_i \in \mathcal{V}. \quad (2)$$

Each token index t_i is projected into a 768-dimensional dense embedding vector:

$$\mathbf{e}_i = \mathbf{W}_e \cdot \text{one_hot}(t_i) + \mathbf{p}_i + \mathbf{s}_i, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_e \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{V}| \times d_e}$ is the token embedding matrix, \mathbf{p}_i is the positional embedding, and \mathbf{s}_i is the segment embedding. The full input embedding matrix is:

$$\mathbf{E} = [\mathbf{e}_0, \mathbf{e}_1, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_e}. \quad (4)$$

The embeddings are processed by L stacked transformer encoder layers of TinyBERT. Each encoder layer consists of a Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) mechanism followed by a position-wise feed-forward network (FFN) with residual connections and normalization:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(l)} = \text{MHSA}(\mathbf{E}^{(l-1)}) + \mathbf{E}^{(l-1)}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{E}^{(l)} = \text{FFN}(\mathbf{H}^{(l)}) + \mathbf{H}^{(l)}, \quad (6)$$

for $l = 1, \dots, L$.

The MHSA computes contextualized representations by attending to all tokens:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V, \quad (7)$$

$$h_i = \text{Attention}(Q_i, K_i, V_i), \quad (8)$$

$$\text{MHSA}(\mathbf{E}) = \text{Concat}(h_1, \dots, h_h)\mathbf{W}^O \quad (9)$$

where $Q = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}^Q$, $K = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}^K$, $V = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}^V$, h is the number of heads, and d_k is the per-head key dimension.

From the last encoder layer $\mathbf{E}^{(L)}$, the hidden state corresponding to the [CLS] token, denoted $\mathbf{h}_{[\text{CLS}]} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_e}$, is extracted as the aggregate representation of the traffic flow. This representation is then input to the proposed attention module for the embedding-channel refinement before the final detection head.

3.2 Attention Module

To enhance the representational capacity of the backbone, we incorporate a lightweight channel attention mechanism inspired by the Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) block [11]. While the transformer's multi-head self-attention captures contextual dependencies across tokens, channel attention complements this by adaptively rescaling embedding dimensions through an input-conditioned squeeze-excitation mechanism. The recalibration is driven by gradients from the detection loss during end-to-end training, thereby refining feature representations before detection.

Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_e}$ denote the output of TinyBERT, where n is the sequence length and d_e is the embedding dimension. The channel attention mechanism operates in two stages:

Squeeze (Global Pooling). For each channel $j \in \{1, \dots, d_e\}$, we compute a global descriptor by averaging across the sequence dimension:

$$s_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_{i,j}, \quad \mathbf{s} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{d_e}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{d_e}. \quad (10)$$

This produces a compact summary vector \mathbf{s} that captures global channel-level statistics.

Excitation (Channel Recalibration). The summary vector \mathbf{s} is passed through a two-layer feed-forward gating mechanism:

$$\mathbf{a} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_2 \delta(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{s})), \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{d_e}{r} \times d_e}$ and $\mathbf{W}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d_e \times \frac{d_e}{r}}$ are learnable parameters, r is the reduction ratio controlling bottleneck size, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the ReLU activation, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid function. The resulting vector $\mathbf{a} \in [0, 1]^{d_e}$ assigns an importance weight to each embedding channel. This mechanism adaptively emphasizes informative channels while suppressing less useful ones, thereby improving discrimination between benign and malicious traffic.

3.3 TinySEED Architecture

The proposed TinySEED approach integrates the TinyBERT backbone with a channel attention module to construct a lightweight yet effective detector for DDoS traffic, as shown in Figure 2. This integration enhances the representational power of TinyBERT by dynamically recalibrating embedding dimensions before detection.

Let $\mathbf{E}^{(L)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_e}$ denote the output embeddings from the final ($L = 6$) TinyBERT encoder layer, where n is the sequence length and $d_e = 768$ is the embedding dimension. The embedding corresponding to the classification token is

$$\mathbf{h}_{[\text{CLS}]} = \mathbf{E}_{0,:}^{(L)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_e}. \quad (12)$$

The subscript $0, :$ in $\mathbf{E}_{0,:}^{(L)}$ denotes selecting the first row (corresponding to the CLS token) and all columns of the embedding matrix $\mathbf{E}^{(L)}$, yielding the final embedding representation of the CLS token at layer L .

Channel Attention Integration. To refine the embedding space, we introduce channel attention, which produces a reweighting vector $\mathbf{a} \in [0, 1]^{d_e}$. The recalibrated embedding matrix is

$$\mathbf{E}' = \mathbf{E}^{(L)} \odot \mathbf{a}, \quad E'_{i,j} = E_{i,j}^{(L)} \cdot a_j, \quad (13)$$

where \odot denotes broadcasted element-wise multiplication. The updated classification token representation becomes

$$\mathbf{h}'_{[\text{CLS}]} = \mathbf{E}'_{0,:}. \quad (14)$$

Detection Head. The recalibrated vector $\mathbf{h}'_{[\text{CLS}]}$ is passed through a dropout layer and then a fully connected detection head:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{W}_c \mathbf{h}'_{[\text{CLS}]} + \mathbf{b}_c, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times d_e}$ and $\mathbf{b}_c \in \mathbb{R}^C$ are trainable parameters, and C is the number of classes. The posterior probabilities are computed by

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{z}), \quad \hat{c} = \arg \max_{i \in \{1, \dots, C\}} \hat{y}_i. \quad (16)$$

Figure 2: Architecture of TinySEED, a framework designed to unmask DDoS attacks. The final decision module outputs the predicted traffic classes.

Table 1: Summary of datasets used for evaluating TinySEED, including number of features, instances, classes, and attack types.

No.	Dataset	#Features	#Instances	#Classes	Attack types
1	BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024	316	653,520	3	17 attack scenarios, multi-vector floods
2	APA-DDoS-Dataset	18	151,200	3	2 attack classes (DDoS-PSH-ACK, DDoS-ACK)
3	DDoS SDN dataset	23	99,254	2	3 types (TCP-SYN, UDP flood, ICMP)
4	CICDDoS2019 (Portmap)	87	29,777	2	12 (train day) / 7 (test day) attack types (e.g., NTP, DNS)
5	CRCDDoS2022	82	134,185	2	Multiple attack families (e.g., Mirai, Slowloris)

End-to-End Formulation. TinySEED can be expressed as the composition of three components:

$$\hat{y} = f_{\text{clf}}(f_{\text{CA}}(f_{\text{TinyBERT}}(s))), \quad (17)$$

where s is the sequentialized traffic flow, f_{TinyBERT} is the backbone encoder, f_{CA} is the channel attention module, and f_{clf} is the final detection. The overall training objective minimizes the cross-entropy loss:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log \hat{y}_{i,c}, \quad (18)$$

with N the number of training samples, $y_{i,c}$ the ground truth one-hot label, and $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ the predicted probability.

Compact View. Equivalently, the full transformation can be summarized as:

$$x \mapsto s \mapsto E^{(L)} \mapsto E' \mapsto h'_{[\text{CLS}]} \mapsto \hat{y}, \quad (19)$$

highlighting the stepwise progression from raw traffic flow to final DDoS detection.

4 Experiments

In this section, we discuss the datasets, the comparative analysis with baseline methods, and the computational efficiency of TinySEED. The datasets are preprocessed by removing duplicate traffic flows and discarding columns with constant values. For each dataset, we randomly split the samples into 70% for training and 30% for

testing using a stratified split to preserve the original class distribution. We do not allocate a separate validation set; instead, we perform a small hyperparameter search on the training split. We select the configuration that achieves the best performance during training and keep this configuration fixed when evaluating on the 30% test split.

The detection head is trained using the AdamW optimizer with an initial learning rate of 3×10^{-5} , a weight decay of 0.01, and a cosine learning rate scheduler with linear warmup. The batch size is set to 128, and training is conducted for up to 6 epochs with an early stopping patience of 3 epochs. All experiments are implemented in PyTorch and executed on a single NVIDIA A100-SXM4 GPU. To ensure fairness, identical preprocessing and training configurations are applied across all datasets and baseline methods. For methods that we re-implement, each model with a dataset configuration is executed three times under the same experimental setup with different random seeds, and the values reported in Tables 2 and 3 are the mean over these three runs.

4.1 Datasets

We use five widely adopted public datasets representing different scenarios to evaluate the proposed method. Table 1 presents the basic statistics of these datasets. Detailed descriptions of each dataset are as follows:

- **BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024** [33] contains over 650k labelled flows of benign and DDoS traffic collected from a

real cloud infrastructure using cPacket monitors, covering 17 attack scenarios and diverse background activities.

- **APA-DDoS-Dataset** [20] consists of 151k flows of labelled benign and DDoS traffic generated in an academic-industry collaborative environment, capturing both application-layer and volumetric attacks.
- **DDoS SDN dataset** [17] provides 99k labelled traffic flows simulating DDoS attacks against software-defined networking (SDN) controllers, reflecting programmable network infrastructures.
- **CICDDoS2019** [34] includes 29k benign and malicious flows generated in a controlled testbed, with diverse DDoS categories such as SYN, UDP, and HTTP floods, along with background traffic.
- **CRCDDoS2022** [9] offers 134k flows combining real and synthetic DDoS traffic with flow-level features, designed to evaluate detection methods under mixed traffic scenarios.

4.2 Comparative Evaluation

In this section, we compare the performance of the proposed TinySEED model with baseline approaches, including conventional machine learning methods, neural architectures, and transformer-based methods. Table 2 presents results across five widely used DDoS detection datasets, where precision, recall, and F1-score are reported as *weighted* averages to account for class imbalance in the datasets. Although some metrics reach 1.0, these results are obtained on a separate 30% test split and are averaged over three independent runs, indicating that they are stable but not due to overfitting.

Conventional methods, such as logistic regression, random forests, and ID3, achieve limited performance on large-scale traffic analysis tasks. For instance, logistic regression achieved 0.93 accuracy on APA-DDoS, while ID3 recorded only 0.78 precision and 0.65 recall on CICDDoS2019. These results indicate that shallow models are unable to effectively capture the temporal and structural patterns inherent in network traffic. Ensemble methods such as random forests achieve high accuracy on CICDDoS2019 (e.g., 0.991 in [31]); however, recall and F1 vary markedly across studies, indicating sensitivity to class imbalance, feature selection, and evaluation protocol. Consequently, accuracy alone is an unreliable proxy for robustness under heterogeneous traffic conditions.

Neural architectures, including CNN+Bi-GRU and SAE-MLP, provide stronger results by learning hierarchical temporal features. CNN+Bi-GRU reaches 0.9935 accuracy on APA-DDoS, and SAE-MLP achieves 0.9975 accuracy on the SDN dataset. However, such models are less suitable for low-latency detection requirements in dynamic environments, as their recurrent components and larger fully connected stacks tend to increase inference latency and memory footprint on long sequences.

Among transformer-based approaches, DDoSBERT, a DistilBERT variant fine-tuned for DDoS detection, demonstrates strong performance in the literature and is considered a baseline approach. DDoSBERT achieves high accuracy (e.g., 0.9861 on BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024 and 0.9996 on CICDDoS2019) but fails to detect subtle attack patterns, particularly in recall-sensitive scenarios. In DDoS detection, even a small number of missed malicious flows

can allow traffic to penetrate defense systems, underscoring the importance of incremental accuracy improvements.

Compared to conventional methods, neural networks, and existing transformer-based approaches, TinySEED offers a compact yet highly effective solution for DDoS detection. Empirical results demonstrate that TinySEED consistently outperforms DDoSBERT across multiple datasets. On BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024, accuracy improves from 0.9861 to 0.9970, a relative improvement of 1.1%. On CICDDoS2019, TinySEED improved the accuracy from 0.9996 to 1.0000, a relative increase of 0.03%. Even marginal improvements in accuracy can substantially strengthen DDoS defence by enhancing intrusion prevention reliability and reducing the likelihood of large-scale service disruption across cloud-edge environments. On the APA-DDoS and DDoS SDN dataset, TinySEED achieves full scores across all metrics, matching or exceeding the distilled baseline while retaining efficiency.

These findings demonstrate that TinySEED effectively addresses the limitations of DistilBERT-based approaches in representational capacity. By combining a robust TinyBERT backbone with channel attention, the model achieves consistently high accuracy and strong generalization across diverse DDoS detection datasets. In the context of DDoS detection, even modest performance improvements are critical, as they directly reduce the number of malicious flows that are otherwise going undetected, enhancing the reliability of network defence systems in real-world deployment scenarios.

4.3 Inference Efficiency

In addition to accuracy, the practical deployment of DDoS detection models requires efficient inference for in-line traffic processing. In this work, we use the average per-instance inference time as our primary measure of computational cost at runtime, since DDoS detectors must operate online on latency-constrained edge devices. Table 3 shows that TinySEED consistently reduces per-instance inference latency compared with DDoSBERT across all evaluated datasets. Specifically, the average inference time is reduced from 9.06 ± 0.02 ms to 8.42 ± 0.33 ms on BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024, and from 0.42 ± 0.00 ms to 0.28 ± 0.00 ms on APA-DDoS-Dataset. Similar latency reductions are observed on DDoS SDN (0.69 ± 0.01 ms to 0.43 ± 0.05 ms), CICDDoS2019 (1.91 ± 0.01 ms to 1.40 ± 0.11 ms), and CRCDDoS2022 (0.64 ± 0.01 ms to 0.62 ± 0.05 ms). Overall, TinySEED achieves approximate inference-time reductions of 7.1%, 33.3%, 37.7%, 26.7%, and 3.1% on BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024, APA-DDoS-Dataset, DDoS SDN, CICDDoS2019, and CRCDDoS2022 datasets, respectively.

These results highlight that integrating the channel attention mechanism into the TinyBERT backbone does not significantly increase inference time. On the contrary, TinySEED reduces inference latency compared to DDoSBERT while providing enhanced detection capabilities. This efficiency makes TinySEED suitable for deployment in latency-sensitive environments, such as cloud and edge networks, where timely detection of malicious traffic is critical for maintaining system availability and security.

Table 2: Comparative analysis of the proposed model against state-of-the-art approaches. Bold indicates the best result.

Dataset	Method	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1
BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024	XGBoost [24]	0.9604	0.9587	0.9604	0.9578
	Naive Bayes [7]	0.5800	-	0.2900	0.1900
	SVM [7]	0.3500	-	0.5000	0.4000
	XGBoost+PU Learning [7]	-	0.9864	0.9945	0.9905
	Decision Tree [27]	0.9680	0.8890	0.8890	0.8890
	K-Nearest Neighbors [27]	0.9540	0.8750	0.8170	0.8410
	Ridge Classifier [27]	0.8770	0.6610	0.6020	0.5900
	Logistic Regression [27]	0.8670	0.5700	0.5970	0.5830
	Linear Support Vector [27]	0.6620	0.5460	0.5470	0.5190
	ExtraTrees [24]	0.9460	0.9444	0.9460	0.9451
	Random Forest [24]	0.9497	0.9474	0.9497	0.9482
	Bagging [24]	0.9567	0.9547	0.9567	0.9551
	DNN-IDS [14]	-	0.9323	0.8192	0.8721
	CNN-IDS [14]	-	0.9192	0.8324	0.8736
	SAINT [19]	0.9700	0.9500	0.9500	0.9600
	TinyBERT	0.9536	0.9614	0.9536	0.9557
	DDoSBERT [10]	0.9861	0.9861	0.9861	0.9861
	TinySEED	0.9970	0.9970	0.9970	0.9970
APA-DDoS	XGBClassifier [29]	0.8510	-	-	-
	GradientBoosting [29]	0.8490	-	-	-
	SGD [23]	0.7700	0.7700	0.6800	0.7600
	SVM [23]	0.7700	0.7700	0.6900	0.7700
	KNN [23]	0.7700	0.7700	0.6900	0.7700
	Naive Bayes [23]	0.8900	0.8900	0.8500	0.8900
	Logistic Regression [23]	0.9300	0.9300	0.9300	0.9100
	CNN + Bi-GRU [18]	0.9935	0.9990	0.9899	0.9908
	Poaching raptor-based DNN [12]	0.9512	0.9630	0.9822	-
	ANN-GWO [35]	0.8815	0.8935	0.8804	0.8916
	CNN [26]	0.8246	0.8370	0.8292	0.8349
	DDoSBERT	1	1	1	1
	TinySEED	1	1	1	1
DDoS SDN dataset	Random Forest [32]	~ 1	-	-	-
	SAE-MLP [1]	0.9975	0.9969	0.9994	0.9982
	CNN + GRU Hybrid Deep Learning Model [8]	0.9970	-	-	-
	DDoSBERT	1	1	1	1
		TinySEED	1	1	1
CICDDoS2019	ID3 [34]	-	0.7800	0.6500	0.6900
	CNN-AD [25]	0.9751	0.9712	-	0.9743
	Random Forest [31]	0.9911	0.9900	-	-
	KNN [31]	0.9845	0.9785	0.9536	0.9658
	Decision tree [31]	0.9825	0.9755	0.9825	0.9789
	Naive Bayes [31]	0.6798	0.6689	0.7598	0.7114
	MLPClassifier [29]	0.7560	-	-	-
	XGBClassifier [29]	0.8790	-	-	-
	GradientBoosting [29]	0.9130	-	-	-
	ARSAE-QGRU [37]	0.9980	-	-	-
DDoSBERT	0.9996	0.9954	0.9951	0.9952	
	TinySEED	1	1	1	1
CRCDDoS2022	GNB, ID3, MLP	0.9950	-	-	-
	Distributed Intelligent Network Element Defense [38]	0.9803	-	-	-
	DDoSBERT	1	1	1	1
		TinySEED	1	1	1

Figure 3: TinySEED learning curves: training loss and accuracy over epochs.

Table 3: Comparison of average per-instance inference time (in milliseconds) between TinySEED and state-of-the-art approaches across different datasets.

Dataset	Method	Average per-instance inference time (ms)
BCCC-cPacket-Cloud-DDoS-2024	DDoSBERT	9.06 ± 0.02
	TinySEED	8.42 ± 0.33
APA-DDoS-Dataset	DDoSBERT	0.42 ± 0.00
	TinySEED	0.28 ± 0.00
DDoS SDN dataset	DDoSBERT	0.69 ± 0.01
	TinySEED	0.43 ± 0.05
CICDDoS2019	DDoSBERT	1.91 ± 0.01
	TinySEED	1.40 ± 0.11
CRCDDoS2022	DDoSBERT	0.64 ± 0.01
	TinySEED	0.62 ± 0.05

4.4 Detailed Performance Analysis

To further evaluate TinySEED, we analyze its learning curves and confusion matrices across all datasets. Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of accuracy (top row) and loss (bottom row) over training epochs. In all datasets, TinySEED shows strong convergence, with training accuracy increasing and loss consistently decreasing. Both metrics stabilize after a few epochs, indicating reliable and stable learning behavior, further validating the performance of the proposed approach.

Figure 4 presents the confusion matrices for each dataset, highlighting per-class detection performance. Notably, for several datasets such as APA-DDoS and the DDoS SDN dataset, TinySEED achieves 100% accuracy, with the confusion matrices showing zero false positives and zero false negatives. This indicates that the model correctly classifies every instance of both normal and attack traffic. For other datasets, the confusion matrices still reflect minimal misdetections, demonstrating that subtle attack patterns are reliably identified.

Together, the training curves and confusion matrices provide complementary evidence of TinySEED’s effectiveness: the model not only converges reliably during training but also maintains robust per-class performance across diverse DDoS datasets. These results further confirm that integrating the SE attention mechanism into TinyBERT significantly enhances its discriminative power for detecting malicious traffic in complex network environments.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This work proposes TinySEED, a lightweight transformer architecture for effective and efficient detection of stealthy DDoS attacks in modern cloud-edge networks. We augment the backbone with a channel-attention module to improve discrimination among diverse DDoS attacks when compared to benign network traces. TinySEED achieves the best overall performance across all datasets, notably on the cloud-DDoS dataset. Compared with other advanced transformer-based models, TinySEED maintains strong detection

Figure 4: Confusion matrices of TinySEED across different datasets.

accuracy while delivering lower inference latency, which is critical for cloud-edge network environments.

In future work, we will extend our work to investigate the root cause of stealthy DDoS attacks and provide decision explanations for TinySEED when deploying it across the cloud-edge continuum.

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